

MATERNAL AND CHILD HEALTH CARE SYSTEM

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Abstract. Maternal and child health (MCH) care is the health service provided to mothers (women in their child bearing age) and children. The targets for MCH are all women in their reproductive age groups, i.e., 15 - 49 years of age, children, school age population and adolescents. Throughout the world, especially in the developing countries, there is an increasing concern and interest in maternal and child health care. Providing access to knowledge on good practices, including exclusive breastfeeding; recognition of early signs of illness or complications of pregnancy, and combining this with prompt treatment and/or referral to higher levels of care, when needed, is vital to saving maternal, neonatal and child lives.

Keyword: maternal, child, health, MCH, women, breastfeeding, pregnancy

INTRODUCTION

Most of the people are busy with business and financial affairs, many people are not aware of the very important health [3]. Nowadays, there are too many teenage couples getting married at a young age. Couple who gets married at a young age often face many difficulties during pregnancy because they have no health knowledge about pregnancy and childbirth. For example, they don't know what to do, what to avoid, and how to prepare during pregnancy, they experience the loss of babies and the loss of mothers' lives during childbirth. We want to write this system to provide knowledge so that there are no such difficulties and losses. The maternal and child health care system plays a pivotal role in safeguarding the well-being of both mothers and children, ensuring their health and resilience. The general objectives of this study are correctly and quickly to reach the health knowledge about mother and child to patients.

PROBLEM

This system is very convenient for young married teenage mothers-to-be, expectant mothers and mothers who are not sure about the health knowledge they should know about maternal and child health. Healthy babies are undoubtedly the most desired wish of expectant mothers. The birth of human life is one of the most important parts of life. Having a healthy baby is the only way to have a happy family life. Therefore, mothers-to-be should pay special attention to follow the dos and don'ts during pregnancy and childbirth [3]. This system is a very good system for mothers and children. Here, we intend to do the design part of the system. Mothers can get accurate knowledge information from this system. In addition,

patients of this system can easily access information about the issues faced by mothers in society.

APPROACH

This system consists of two roles. There are Administrator and Patient. On the patient side, there are two types: visitors who have not logged in and signed in patients. Visitors who have not yet logged in can view the main page, can read the updating news, can view the announcements, can read the health knowledge about the maternal and child health and can see the contact page. If patients want to get appointment schedule, the patient must login. Patients who are signed in must be able to view and edit their logged in profiles, and provide the feedback from feedback page. (Patients must be allowed to submit the feedback, view profile and getting appointment if they are logged in.). There, a contact page has been added so that users can easily contact the admin when needed. After that the patients can log out and the system will stop working.

On the administrator side, the admin must login first. After logged in, admin can view the information of users. Admin also can upload news and announcements. Moreover, admin can view the news and announcement. Admin not only update news, announcement but also delete news and announcement. Admin can see the feedback of the patients who use this system. Admin can see the appointments that was booked by patients. Admin can add new users in vaccination form and update already done vaccination patients. Admin can also view the vaccination records of patients and retrieve this vaccination records for each patient.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes [2]. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. In the database, there are six data tables for administrator and five data tables for the user. The tables are users, feedback, news, announcement, appointment and medicine. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

The design of each page of the maternal and child health care system has been carefully designed and simpler. Talking about the maternal and child health care, the patients (visitors) can easily read the health education, can see the main page for department, can view the announcements from department and can know how to contact the caregivers with just having the internet on your mobile phone or other devices without logging in. If the patients are logged in, they can view the profile of their logged in detail, can get the schedule appointment for pregnant women and can give the feedback for their opinion to improve this system or another want to say. If the patients are in place where there is no internet, the fact that the patients cannot use the maternal and child health care system will be a disadvantage.

Therefore, we will continue to work hard to make it easier in the future and even in places where there is no internet. This system is a place where patients can directly connect online instead of going to the department. Mainly, this system which can help the users to get the right information for their health.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

The Maternal and Child Health Care system is implemented for the maternal and child health department under the department of township Public Health (Hinthada). The maternal and child health care system is a critical component of public health, ensuring the well-being of mothers, infants, and children. This system can significantly improve health outcomes for mothers and children. This includes prenatal and postnatal services, improved child health, development and also includes immunizations, nutrition programs, and educational resources. Public health education campaigns are essential to raise awareness about the importance of maternal and child health. This includes educating mothers about prenatal care, nutrition, immunizations, and breastfeeding. In conclusion, improving maternal and child health care systems is critical to achieving broader public health goals and a healthy future for all.

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